

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF HOUSING AND COMMUNAL ECONOMY IN THE REGION UNDER GLOBALIZATION

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modernization, utilities.

In order to reduce poverty in the regions and improve the standard of living of the population, providing high-quality housing and communal services, new approaches to the modernization of communal services, adapting them to new modern technical requirements, digitalization of local communal services and compliance with norms and quality standards are one of the most urgent issues of today.

A distinctive feature of each period is the conformity to a specific model of the quality of housing and public services. As a dynamic economic category in the development of the quality of housing and communal services, we can witness the formation of the following academic periods:

- ✓ philosophical (first period)
- ✓ mechanic (second term)
- ✓ cybernetic (third period)
- ✓ systematic (fourth period)
- ✓ information (fifth period)

In his research, E.A. Ionita recognized that mass-consumed services (utility services, medical, educational services, etc.) have a special place in the development of the service sector in the region. These services, based on public management and public-private partnerships, bring additional prosperity to the attractiveness of the region. He emphasized that while education plays a fundamental role in the formation and improvement of human resources, utility services are important to provide the necessary infrastructure for industrial development.[2]

In his scientific views, I.A. Savina recognized that utility services as a dynamic economic category are manifested through the process of reproduction (production, distribution, exchange, consumption of services) and the main management functions are information, stability, observation, management, adaptation, and stimulation. [3] In his research work, he described the following information functions of the quality of utility services:

- ✓ uncertainty in matching consumer characteristics and assessing the amount of information obtained;
- ✓ usefulness of information;
- ✓ dynamic mechanism of information;
- ✓ the availability of relevant information in the selection of the necessary information.

Organization of utility services based on CIM (Common Information Model) and CALS (Continuous Acquisition and Life cycle Support) technologies stated in his research work that quality improvement and development efficiency will increase with the transition to its use.[4]

A. Maslow in his work entitled "Motivation and personality" stated that the population's need for housing and communal services can be divided into two sub-levels, namely, physiological needs and security needs. He commented that these needs are very important in meeting the needs of housing and household services for the population.[5]

In his articles, A.V. Keshelava says that the complexity of public utility service sector systems (systems based on the use of information technologies) requires taking into account the specific features of digital technologies. It recognizes that it is responsible for the intellectual processing of information about changes in the state of complex objects and ensures the selection of management decisions.[6]

E. Brynolfsson and L. Hittchlar, as a result of studying the activities of 527 large American firms, the authors say that additional assets (assets that change under the influence of information technology, the experience and skills of employees, communication tools and technologies, the quality of decision-making, changes in business processes, etc.) plays an important role, and over time, the results of the implementation of digital technologies will gradually appear in the development phase.[7]

According to T.M. Kharinova, it is recommended to develop and implement a set of regulatory and technical documents (for example, service standards, guidelines, model contracts, etc.) within the framework of improving the quality of housing and communal services and implementing the monitoring function.[8]

New directions in the socio-economic development of developed countries are, first of all, innovative economy based on the idea of Y. Schumpeter, [9] development trends of post-industrial society based on the American scientist D. Bell, [10] J. Hawkins' theory of knowledge economy or creative economy, [11] Y.

We can witness Benkler's concepts put forward in his scientific works called "Digital economy", introduced by D. Tapscott and called "digital economy"[12].

In the following years, we can witness that the development of the field of communal services was studied at the meso, micro and macro levels in the scientific works of many scientists. However, although some aspects of the development of the field of communal services in rural areas have been covered in many scientific works, the differences between the city and the countryside and the digital transformation of communal services in rural areas have not been fully explored. In this regard, we can witness that a whole concept has not been formed, with a lot of debates among economists.

In general, all the definitions given above indicate that services satisfy the needs of any subject of the market economy and are an activity that is useful to him. But these definitions still do not fully cover the specific quality improvement aspects of communal services.

The ideas and practical experience of the foreign and domestic scientists that we have analyzed above show that it creates a real opportunity for citizens to manage their personal and joint property, which in turn helps to improve the living conditions of the population.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on January 25, 2020, "... active transition to the digital economy will be one of our most important tasks in the next 5 years, although our country rose to the 8th place in 2019 according to the "International Information and Communication Technologies Development Index", we are still far behind. Most of the ministries, agencies, and enterprises are completely far from digital technologies, and it is true..."[13] they said. Because of this, we need to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies to achieve progress. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension. After all, digital technologies are rapidly entering all areas of the world today.

During the historical development of mankind, one of the main and important tasks has been the issue of improving the standard of living of the population. The standard of living of the population depends on the availability of material goods related to living and the level of organization of services provided in the social sphere.

In turn, spiritual and material blessings are the product of human thinking, the result of effective work. Currently, according to the method adopted by the United Nations, the rating of the level of development of the countries of the

world is determined not according to their economic potential or military power, but according to the level of development of the population's lifestyle and human resources.

The standard of living of the population depends on the social policy and the development of the social sector in the country. In turn, the social sphere consists of infrastructures that provide material and spiritual benefits to the population.

It should be noted that solving the tasks of gas supply, electricity supply, water supply, waste management of the housing and communal economy - increasing the level and quality of services to the population should be provided in harmony with the implementation of measures to protect the external environment.

In this study, the main element of the infrastructure of the housing and communal service sector of Kashkadarya region, the results of the innovative development of "Housing and communal farms" are highlighted, and the following are proposed according to the main goal of the scientific research:

- provision of housing and communal services with innovative information technologies and logistics;
- training of qualified personnel by combining housing and communal services with education and advanced technology;
- development of a system for evaluating the innovative development of housing and communal services;
- improvement of the management system of enterprises in the field of housing and communal economy through innovative technologies;
- transformation of innovative infrastructure objects that provide comfortable and safe living conditions for the population;
- the introduction of innovative technologies into the complex of housing and communal economy and, as a result, the improvement of the quality of housing and communal services, today remain the urgent tasks of reforming this sector of the economy.

One of the promising means of changing the situation in the field of housing and communal services in accordance with the above-mentioned goals is the development of digital innovative infrastructure. A distinctive feature of the innovative development of housing and communal services is the selection of the most viable directions using the mechanism of innovative development of competition.

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